

RESTORE

Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage
Technology in Order to Raise Economic and
environmental sustainability of DHC

D5.6 - Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case III: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry

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Summary:

This deliverable presents part of the activities and outcomes of Task 5.4 within RESTORE EU project [European Commission, 2021], which focuses on demonstrating the performance and replicability of the RESTORE integrated system in several facilities. The task consists of the implementation, optimization, and validation of six real use-cases through their digital representations, using the RESTORE Simulation Web Platform (IPSE GO). These virtual models aim to replicate real district heating and cooling (DHC) networks across diverse industrial and geographical contexts in Europe, including biomass and solar systems, cement and paper industries, steelworks, geothermal applications, and university campuses.

Deliverable D5.6 deals with the implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case III: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry. The information provided in this document builds upon collaboration among TU-WIEN, ANDRITZ, SIMTECH, CENER and all RESTORE development partners.

The document details the methodological framework used to implement the Use-Case III (related to Sub-task 5.4.3), drawing on technical input from WP1 to WP4, and presenting simulation models for Use-Case III within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, resulting from the integration of the RESTORE concept in DH coupled to the Paper Mills Industry. For each use-case, the partners defined specific system boundaries, components, and operational conditions, which were then simulated and optimized in the platform. The work provides both a technical validation of the RESTORE concept, economic outcomes assessment and a structured dataset to support environmental impact assessment. Ultimately, the insights gathered here serve as a cornerstone for developing large-scale replication strategies in Task 5.5, facilitating broader deployment of RESTORE technologies across Europe, [European Commission, 2019].

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Baseline Plant.....	7
2.1. Plant description: MONDI SCP, Ružomberok	8
3. RESTORE TCES Integration.....	11
3.1. Use Case definition	11
3.2. IPSE GO Platform	12
3.3. Input Data.....	13
3.4. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation	15
3.4.1. Charge Model.....	16
3.4.2. Discharge Model (without ORC):	17
3.4.1. Discharge Model (ORC included)	18
4. Results.....	19
4.1. Process Simulations	19
4.1.1. The Charging Mode.....	19
4.1.2. The Discharging Mode	20
4.1.3. Global data for charging/discharging at $P_{R_{th}}=14,32$ MW	21
4.2. Economic Insights	24
5. Conclusions	25

1. Introduction

Subtask 5.4.3 (Use-Case III - Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry) addresses the implementation and virtual replication of the RESTORE TCES concept within a Pulp and Paper Mill, see [European Commission, 2023/1] [European Commission, 2023/2], feeding the district heating network of Ružomberok in Slovakia. This facility combines recovery boilers, biomass boilers and gas boilers for peak load to supply both power and heat for plant operation as well as residential heating demands. The objective is to integrate these suppliers into the RESTORE simulation framework to assess their performance under different operational conditions and control strategies.

Led by ANDRITZ in cooperation with TU-WIEN, with the technical support of SIMTECH and contributions from CENER, the work involves defining the systems mass and heat balances integration, available energy sources (biomass and recovery boilers) and thermal chemical energy storage (TCES), [Frazzica, 2019], configuration. The model is implemented within the IPSE GO platform, see [SIMTECH GmbH, 2023/1], [SIMTECH GmbH, 2023/2], enabling interactive simulation, control testing, and optimization of system sizing and parameters involved. Additionally, a dedicated economic and financial evaluation outlines the indicators to be evaluated.

This document is structured to present a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of the Use-Case III. It begins with a description of the baseline plant, including its technical background and configuration (Section 2). Section 3 focuses on the integration of the RESTORE TCES system, detailing the use-case definition, the role of the IPSE GO Platform, the input data (including assumptions and refinements), and the virtual implementation steps. Section 4 presents the results, encompassing both process simulations and economic outcomes. The economic analysis includes investment and operational costs, levelized cost metrics, and broader financial indicators. The document concludes with key findings (Section 5) and references (Section 6), [SIMTECH GmbH, 2023/3], [SIMTECH GmbH, 2023/4].

General information about the Use-Case III and its paper mill plant, MONDI in Ružomberok, Slovakia, is described in the public documentation of “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling” concerning WP5 Task T5.4 implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, using the Simulation Web Platform”, available in the project’s Zenodo Community account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>).

2. Baseline Plant

Use-Case III integrates RESTORE with different heat sources in DH of a paper mill plant, MONDI in Ružomberok, in Slovakia. The Use-Case III application area involves the analysis of potential configurations for integrating the RESTORE technology into plants of the Pulp and Paper Industry connected to DH and RES. Expected goals for achievement include the maximization of the renewable energy integration and optimize WEH utilization from the plant for highly efficient seasonal heat storage, [European Commission, 2025].

MONDI SCP in Ružomberok is one of MONDI's largest plants and is the biggest integrated mill producing paper and pulp in Slovakia, with a production capacity of 560,000 tonnes of uncoated fine paper, 66,000 tonnes of packaging paper and 100,000 tonnes of market pulp. After its latest investment into a new recovery boiler, the mill is 100% energy self-sufficient with over 94% of its energy coming from renewable resources. The wood comes from certified, well-managed forests. The production continuously decreases footprint on the environment. Part of the heat produced by the Mondi mill is used for the district heating system in the form of 5 bar steam. Steam enters a heat exchanger station, where heat exchangers transfer heat into water. Hot water is pumped via a distribution network into the city, local heat exchangers and flowing back to the steam/ water heat exchanger station to gain heat again.

Figure 1: Mondi SCP Plant (source: <https://www.profisteelholding.sk/en/reference/mondi-scp-2>)

About the community addressed within Use-Case III: Paper has been produced in Ružomberok for over 300 years. The abundance of the raw materials like wood, water, and energy has had a favourable influence on the development of the mill. In early years, the mill was far away from residential areas, but in the course of urban development, the city has spread and the mill is now in the heart of the Ružomberok area, which embeds 49,035 km²

with 40.84% of forest land and a population of ~5.4 million. The main industries of the region are: automobile, chemical, iron ore processing, and pulp and paper.

The virtual integration of the RESTORE system with Mondi SCP Pulp & Paper plant system, aims at maximizing renewable energy integration and optimum WEH utilization from the factory for an efficient seasonal storage of heat (for the sake of simplification, in Use-Case III, day/night load variations instead of seasonal ones are considered). The expected outcome includes the reduction of the GHG through a high increment in the RES share and the waste heat capacity factor.

In the following, the pulp and paper mill of MONDI in Ružomberok is described in its original situation, illustrated by the scheme in Figure 2, to support the development and concepts concerning thermochemical energy storage for the paper mill to cope with day / night load variations concerning the heat demand of the local district heating network.

2.1. Plant description: MONDI SCP, Ružomberok

Figure 2: Scheme of the steam network of the MONDI SCP PLANT in Ružomberok, Slovakia.

Steam Generators:

The steam network is fed by two recovery boilers R2 and R3, two gas fired peak load boilers P1 and P2 as well as by one biomass boiler KDO. The max. steam production is >400 t/h. The gas fired boilers are under operation in winter for about 2 months, due to the fact that district heating as well as paper mill demand are about 30 t/h higher during winter period. When under operation the peak load boilers feed to the high pressure distribution network at 6,3 MPa.

Recovery boiler R2 consumes steam from the distribution network with an operating pressure level of 4,2 MPa and feeds steam turbine TG7 as well as RS 8/0,5.

The biomass boiler KDO feeds its steam directly to the 4,2 MPa steam network from where RS 1,3, RS 0,6 as well as the two steam turbines TG1 and TG2 are supplied. Both TG1 and TG2 are back pressure turbines with an exhaust pressure of 0,6 MPa.

Recovery boiler R3 is, like R2, continuously operated and feeds RS9 as well as condensation turbine TG9.

Steam pressure levels:

The steam network finds four pressure levels at 6,3 MPa, 4,2 MPa, 1,3 MPa and 0,6 MPa. The highest pressure distribution network is fed by the gas fired boilers P1 and P2, which are only operated in winter, as mentioned above. So even back pressure turbine TG3 is active only if P1 and/or P2 are under operation.

RS 0,6, RS 1,3 and TG3 are fed by the the 6,3 MPa distributor; furthermore RS1,3, TG3, RS9, TG9, TG1 and TG2 are bleeding to the steam distribution network with an operating pressure of 1,3 MPa.

The lowest pressure steam distribution network (0,6 MPa) is fed by RS 0,8, TG3, RS 9, TG1, TG2, RS 8/0,5 and TG7. From the 0,6 MPa network the following consumers are fed: PM1, PM 16, PM 17 PM 18, PM 19, NP, the district heating network (City), the causter, the evaporator, the machine, VLINK as well as ODPL.

Table 1: List of main components of MONDI plant:

Comp.	Name	Description	Remark
City	District heating heat exchanger	Condenser	-
Dist	Steam distribution track		
Evap	Evaporator	-	-
Kaust	Kauster	-	-
KDO	Biomass boiler	-	-
Mach.	Pulp & Paper device	-	-
ODPL	Feed water tank	-	-
P1, P2	Peak load boilers	Only in winter operated	Gas fired
PM	Papermaschine	-	-
R2, R3	Recovery boilers	Continuously operated	-
RS	Pulp & Paper device	-	-
TG	Steam turbine	-	-
VLINK	Fibre line batch digester	-	-

Further remarks:

- There is no cooling demand within the network.
- All enthalpy streams (e. g. in condensate) are used down to 50 °C.
- Demand for slightly superheated 1 bar steam exists for degasification
- The 30000 GJ steam production is limited by the district heating demand of the city.

3. RESTORE TCES Integration

This chapter defines and develops the Use-Case III, virtually integrating the RESTORE solution into the MONDI Paper Mill plant in Ružomberok, initially described in Chapter 2.

3.1. Use Case definition

The definition of the Use-Case III is based on the following considerations:

- Currently the biomass boiler is following the electricity price, value for biomass steam production is 4 €/GJ.
- During winter period the gas fired boilers must be operated for about two months due to the enhanced demand for district heating and paper mill (30 t/h more steam), value for gas boiler produced steam is 8 €/GJ.
- There is no need for seasonal storage, because 30000 GJ for one month relates to 120000 €, which doesn't justify any investment.
- It would be beneficial to maximize the condensing turbines operation in case of high power prices. The electricity prices are at 100 € during the night, reach a morning peak between 6:00-8:00 am, and remain at 150 € until 7 pm.
- Digester operation is discontinuous, when digester is under operation, power production goes down
- The capacity of the condensing turbines is at 140 t/h.
- The total steam capacity at the mill, if all boilers are operated is > 400 t/h.
- Heat supply from the paper mill to the city varies between 5000 GJ/month in summer up to 30000 GJ/month in winter,
- All condensates are used within the mill, only condensate with a temperature lower than 50 °C is available.
- Excess 5 bar steam of the mill could be fed to the condensing turbine (capacity 140 t/h). a simple approach is to assume 0,14 MWel per t/h steam.

Table 2: Time dependent demand for district heating and price for electricity:

Time span	Steam demand for DH	Electricity price	Comments
h	t/h	€/MWh	-
20:00-6:00	19	100	10 t/h steam for 1,4 MWel, Biomass boiler would have additional potential of steam production at 4 €/GJ but is not under operation due to reduced DH demand and lower price

06:00-8:00	27	250	Biomass boiler is under full load (+20 t/h) to produce maximum electricity (22 t/h 3,08 MWeI)
08:00-10:00	24	150	Biomass boiler under full load
18:00-20:00	27	230	Biomass boiler under full load

Remark for using a heat storage:

The economic output must be maximized under fulfilling always DH-requirements. The biomass boiler can be operated always at 100 % load (condensation turbine capacity at 140 t/h).

3.2. IPSE GO Platform

The RESTORE Virtual Tool used to simulate the use case is powered by the IPSE GO Platform, which is a web-based simulation and optimization environment designed to support the virtual implementation of complex energy systems. Within the RESTORE project, it plays a central role in the digital representation and testing of six real-world use-cases, each reflecting distinct district heating and cooling (DHC) configurations. The platform allows users to model, simulate, and optimize integrated energy systems combining components such as thermochemical storage, renewable heat sources, and thermodynamic cycles.

One of the core strengths of IPSE GO lies in its flexibility and modular design. It supports the integration of a wide variety of components and subsystems, enabling partners to replicate specific operational settings and boundary conditions from each use-case. For each virtual scenario, the platform facilitates the configuration of heat sources, sinks, storage units, and control strategies, ensuring that the simulation mirrors the physical dynamics of the real installation as accurately as possible.

In addition to basic system modelling, IPSE GO incorporates advanced optimization tools that help evaluate the system's performance under different operational parameters. Users can simulate dynamic behavior over time, analyze energy flows, and test alternative layouts or control algorithms. This supports the identification of the most effective technical solutions for each local context and ensures that the RESTORE concept is not only functional but also efficient and scalable.

The platform also plays a key role in promoting replicability and transparency across the project. Its cloud-based nature facilitates collaboration between project partners, enabling remote access, version tracking, and shared testing environments. By consolidating all use-cases in a unified digital workspace, IPSE GO enables systematic benchmarking, comparison, and validation of the RESTORE solution across diverse European settings.

3.3. Input Data

Charging Mode:

In *Figure 3*, the implementation of the thermochemical reactor to the steam network of the plant for the charging mode is shown. For charging, steam from the 5 bar(a) network is used to heat up the thermal oil to its target temperature of about 140 °C. The heat input to the TCS-reactor, is done via two steps:

- a) the condenser of the reversible ORC/HP-cycle
- b) the thermal oil / steam-HEX

In the thermal oil/steam-HEX the oil is heated up to 140 °C to enable the dehydration process of the TCM in the TCS-reactor. Under ambient pressure for CuSO₄ a reactor temperature of 125 °C is necessary. The reversible ORC/HP-cycle is during the charging process operated in heat pump mode. Heat input to the working medium takes place in the preheater where the steam coming from the TO/Steam heat exchanger is condensed and in the TCS steam condenser, where the, during the dehydration process, released steam is condensed and collected in the water storage vessel.

Figure 3: Charging concept for the MONDI SCP PLANT

The major part of the 5 bar(a) steam is fed to:

- the condensing steam turbine;
- to the district heating condenser to heat up the water to about 110 °C;
- and
- to the digester for the paper mill.

3.4. IPSE GO Virtual Case implementation

In the following the Use-Case III is defined and the models for charging and discharging are explained.

Use-Case III - IPSE GO-Model for the charging mode:

The IPSE GO model for the charge case is shown in *Figure 5*. The UC is based on the assumption that all the excess steam of 20 t/h is used to dehydrate TCS-material. This leads to a thermal TCS-reactor power of $P_{R_{th}}=14,32$ MW. In addition even a case study for a thermal power of 1 MW was done.

Use-Case III - IPSE GO-Model for the discharging mode without ORC:

The IPSE GO model for the discharge case is shown in *Figure 6*. The UC is based on the assumption that the TCS-reactor is operated with the same power $P_{R_{th}}$ as in the charging case. Additionally is assumed that all released heat is used for the DH-network.

Use-Case III - IPSE GO-Model for the discharging mode with ORC:

The IPSE GO model for the discharge case is shown in *Figure 7*. The UC is based on the assumption that the TCS-reactor is operated with $P_{R_{th}} = 1$ MW; heat output is used for ORC-operation and the DH-network.

3.4.1. Charge Model

Figure 5: IPSE GO-Model of Charging Process

3.4.2. Discharge Model (without ORC):

Figure 6: IPSE GO-Model of Discharging Process without ORC-process

3.4.1. Discharge Model (ORC included)

Figure 7: IPSE GO-Model of Discharging Process with ORC-process

4. Results

This section presents the main outcomes of the implementation of the virtual Use-Case III, with the description of the Process Simulations (4.1), including: the results of the charging mode scenario; and the respective to the results of the discharging mode scenario; as well as some economic aspects of the overall simulated system (4.2). Together, these results provide insights for the technical feasibility of the proposed system.

4.1. Process Simulations

Here we present the results of the system simulations performed within IPSE GO, under different operating modes, considering the charging and the discharging modes.

4.1.1. The Charging Mode

The overall results concerning the charging mode of the Use-Case III model, can be summarized as follows:

In *Figure 5* the IPSE GO-Model for the charging case is shown. The simulation has been done under the assumption that a steam mass flow of $m_{Dot_Steam} = 20$ t/h, is fed to the thermal oil loop transferring the heat to the TCS-reactor. This results in thermal power of the thermochemical reactor of $P_{R_th} = 14,32$ MW. For the stage of development, this thermal power doesn't reflect reactor sizes to be realized now, but it covers the requirements of the MONDI SCP plant. The high thermal load causes high mass flows of TCS-material $m_{Dot_TCS_hyd} = 72,41$ t/h, fed to the reactor. This value corresponds to a mass flow of dehydrated material of $m_{Dot_TCS_dehyd} = 72,41$ t/h.

Due to the fact that the material has to be dehydrated at a temperature level of (above) $\vartheta_R = 125$ °C, the steam leaves the thermal oil/steam HEX with temperature 136,5 °C. This steam can be used to heat up the return water from the district heating network, where a heat flow of $Q_{Dot_S} = 388$ kW can be transferred. Another source, for heating the return water, is the condensation of the steam, released during the dehydration process of the TCS-material ($Q_{Dot_S_dh} = 388$ kW). The following table gives a summary of the calculated values:

Table 3: Steam flows in paper mill during charging

Mill Steam Flow		
Description	Value	Unit
total	34,21	t/h
To turbine	14,21	t/h
To TCS-reactor	20	t/h

Table 4: TCS-reactor parameters during charging

TCS-Performance			
Description	Value	Unit	Remark
Thermal power	14,32	MW	of reactor
solid flow in	50,69	t/h	-
solid flow out	36,79	t/h	-
water flow out	13,9	t/h	-

Table 5: Heat pump parameters during charging

Heat Pump-Performance			
Description	Value	Unit	Remark
Compressor power	576,4	kW	of reactor
solid flow in		t/h	-
solid flow out	36,79	t/h	-
water flow out	13,9	t/h	

Due to recovering the released dehydration steam, the mass flow of steam necessary for supplying the district heating network is reduced by 13,96 t/h.

4.1.2. The Discharging Mode

The overall results concerning the discharging mode of the Use-Case III model, can be summarized as follows:

Discharging without ORC-Module:

The IPSE GO model for the discharging process is shown in *Figure 6*, which represents the case, where the ORC-module is not activated. The reason for selecting this option was the condensation temperature level of the ORC-process, preventing sufficient use of this heat for return water preheating of the DH-network. So by use of a thermal oil cycle, heat is directly transferred to water, rising its temperature from 60 °C to 110 °C. The following Tables summarizes the results:

Table 6: TCS-reactor parameters during discharging without ORC-cycle

TCS-Performance			
Description	Value	Unit	Remark
Thermal power	14,32	MW	of reactor
solid flow in	313,40	t/h	-
solid flow out	431,70	t/h	-
water flow out	120,70	t/h	-

Table 7: Steam turbine production and electricity demand

Turbine production and electricity demand		
Turbine		
Description	Value	Unit
Extra steam to turbine	20,66	t/h
Power production	2,89	MW
Electric demand for discharging		
Electric power	120,70	kW

4.1.3. Global data for charging/discharging at $P_{R_{th}}=14,32$ MW

Table 8: Operational data for the total system at $P_{R_{th}}=14,32$ MW

Operational data		
Description	Value	Unit
Charging		
Day under operation	300	d
Charging hrs. per day	10	MW
Total energy charged per day	143,2	MWh

Total energy charged per year	4,925*10 ⁴	MWh
TCM produced per day charging	585,1	tons
Discharging		
Discharging hours per day	1,174	h
Total energy discharg. per day	16,81	MWh
Discharging hours per year	352,2	h
Total energy discharged per year	5043	MWh

Discharging with ORC-Module:

In *Figure 7* the discharging model including ORC-process is shown. Differently to the simulations before (for charging and discharging), the thermal reactor power now was set to $P_{R_{th}}=1$ MW. A power class, which could be reached within the next steps of development. In case of coupling the ORC-process to the TCS-system, one is faced to the relatively low condensation temperature level of the ORC-cycle at about 35 °C. Therefore condensation heat can't be used for preheating the DH return water ($\vartheta_{DH_{ret}}=60$ °C) and has to be released to the ambient ($Q_{Dot_{cond}} = 521,1$ kW). Heating of DH-water is performed within two steps:

- 1) Preheating by using a low temperature recuperator of the ORC,
- 2) Final heating by the thermal oil/water heat exchanger transfer at the exit of the TC-reactor.

The following tables give an overview about the results for the discharging procedure with ORC:

Table 9: TCS-reactor parameters during discharging with ORC

TCS-Performance			
Description	Value	Unit	Remark
Thermal power	1,00	MW	of reactor
solid flow in	21,88	t/h	-
solid flow out	30,15	t/h	-
water flow in	8,432	t/h	-

Table 10: ORC parameters during discharging with ORC

ORC-Performance		
Description	Value	Unit
Expander power	46,07	kW
Heat source q_trans	646,50	kW
Heat sink q_trans	521,10	kW

Table 11: Turbine parameters during discharging with ORC

Turbine production and electricity demand		
Turbine		
Description	Value	Unit
Extra steam to turbine	0,6275	t/h
Power production	0,1339	MW

4.2. Economic Insights

In the context of the RESTORE use-case simulations, several key economic and financial parameters were evaluated to assess the viability and cost-effectiveness of the integrated energy systems. These parameters included the Total Investment Cost (**CAPEX**), which captures the upfront expenses associated with system components, installation, and commissioning. In addition, Operational and Maintenance Costs (**OPEX**) was assessed to account for recurring expenses over the system's lifetime. Levelized Cost of Heat (**LCOH**) and or Storage (**LCOS**), [Schmidt, 2019] was used as a core financial indicator, providing a normalized cost per unit of useful thermal energy delivered. Other important parameters include the **Payback Period**, which estimates the time required to recover the investment, and Net Present Value (**NPV**) and Internal Rate of Return (**IRR**), which were used to evaluate long-term profitability. The analysis-study is still under revision and intends to incorporate sensitivity assessments on energy prices, subsidies, or carbon costs to reflect economic uncertainty and policy implications in a further publication. These metrics collectively will support the comparison of use-case configurations and guide the selection of optimal, replicable solutions across various European contexts. To avoid redundancy across various deliverables, detailed information regarding the economic analysis of this and the other use cases will be consolidated in deliverable D1.9, 'Report on the Assessment of Socio-Economic Sustainability (V2 Final).

5. Conclusions

The RESTORE solution proposed and adapted to the Use-Case III was comprehensively described in this document.

Therefore, a case of application has been defined, where in the first approach the thermal power of the reactor was set to $P_{R_th}=14,32$ MW. This assumption was made to use all the steam, which can be generated, when the biomass boiler is under full load operation. In total, this assumption leads to a steam flow of 34,21 t/h, where 20 t/h are fed to the thermochemical reactor, whereas the rest (14,21 t/h) is spent to the steam turbine, producing an electric power of 1,4 MW. This case leads for charging to a very high mass flow of TCS, fed to the TCS-reactor (50,69 t/h), while 36.79 t/h are extracted. Both values are pure solid flows, not considering the oil, which is suspending the solid material.

In case of discharging at a thermal power of $P_{R_th}=14,32$ MW, the process was assumed to be operated without ORC-cycle. The reason for, is the relatively low condensation temperature of the ORC-process, which prevents from using the heat of condensation for heating up the return water of the district heating network. To operate the TCS-reactor at 14,32 MW causes high mass flows of solid matter to and from the reactor (feed: 313,4 t/h, extract; 431,7 t/h).

As an alternative and for comparison the discharging case, including ORC for electricity production, for a thermal power of the TCS-reactor of $P_{R_th}=1$ MW was analysed. Solids flow to the reactor is therefor reduced to 21,88 t/h; solids flow out to 30,15 t/h (due to the added water at hydration). At a heat input to the ORC-cycle of 646,5 kW an electric power of 46,07 kW is produced and a waste heat flow to the ambient of 521,1 kW occurs, which can't be used in the current plant configuration.

Summarized, the findings presented in this report show:

- that the TCS-system can be used for supporting the DH-network sufficiently, only if the system is used without the ORC-cycle at discharging. To overcome this problem the condensation pressure of the ORC should be enhanced (to allow higher temperatures for heat release) or the temperature of the DH-network changes, e. g. to allow for using a heat pump.
- that the described case, using a TCS-reactor with a thermal power of $P_{R_th}=14,32$ MW, (chosen to calculate the resulting operating parameters) leads to inappropriate high values concerning solid mass flows, reactor size and volume of storage vessels, especially for long term storage.
- that, considering a realistic upscaled TCS-reactor with a thermal power of $P_{R_th}=1-2$ MW, could be a reliable possibility for the paper mill to supply for certain demand in future.

Overall, the findings presented in this report reinforce the suitability of the integration of the RESTORE proposed solution to paper mill plants, as virtually demonstrated in Use-Case III.

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